

Supplementary Figure 1: Feature set PCA plots coloured by ALSFRS-R progression

Supplementary Figure 2: Feature set PCA plots coloured by EI Escorial Diagnostic Classification

Supplementary Figure 3: Feature set PCA plots coloured by data split (participants with ALSFRS-R score progression data)

Supplementary Figure 4: Feature set PCA plots coloured by data split (all participants)

Supplementary Figure 5: mtry optimisation results

Supplementary Figure 6: Bias-variance decomposition analysis: ALSFRS-R progression

Supplementary Figure 7: Bias-variance decomposition analysis: ALSFRS-R progression seed variance for each feature set

Supplementary Figure 8: Bias-variance decomposition analysis: El Escorial Diagnostic Criteria

Supplementary Figure 9: Bias-variance decomposition analysis: ALSFRS-R progression seed variance for each feature set

Supplementary Figure 11: Model Performance plots by feature set (ALSFRS-R- holdout set)

ALSFRS Model Performance by Feature Set (Holdout Set)

Supplementary Figure 11: Model Performance plots by feature set (El Escorial- holdout set)

Escorial Model Performance by Feature Set (Holdout Set)

Supplementary Figure 12: Confusion matrices: Random Forests, ALSFRS-R Progression

A Random Forest - Metadata - ALSFRS-R Progression (Holdout)

B Random Forest - Proteomics - ALSFRS-R Progression (Holdout)

C Random Forest - Transcriptomics - ALSFRS-R Progression (Holdout)

D Random Forest - Transcriptomics + Proteomics - ALSFRS-R Progression (Holdout)

E Random Forest - All Features - ALSFRS-R Progression (Holdout)

Supplementary Figure 13: Confusion matrices: Random Forests, El Escorial Diagnostic criteria

Supplementary Figure 14: Confusion matrices: Optuna Decision Trees, ALSFRS-R Progression

Supplementary Figure 15: Confusion matrices: Optuna Decision Trees, El Escorial Criteria

Supplementary Figure 16: Confusion matrices: Optuna Random Forests, ALSFRS-R Progression

Supplementary Figure 17: Confusion matrices: Optuna Random Forests, El Escorial Diagnostic Criteria

Supplementary Figure 19: Correlation Matrices for proteomics feature set

Correlation Matrix - proteomics Features

Supplementary Figure 20: Correlation Matrices for transcriptomic feature set

Correlation Matrix - transcriptomics Features

